

"ANALYSIS OF SOLUTIONS TO REDUCE THE IMPACT OF VEHICLE TRANSPORT ON THE ENVIRONMENT"

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Anatotsiya : To reduce the negative impact of industry and transport as much as possible, to achieve implementation of large-scale activities in enterprises and organizations and, as a result, to improve the level of atmospheric air quality. 10% reduction of pollutant emissions into the atmosphere (including 7% from transport and 3% from industry); 80 percent of vehicles use gas fuel and to ensure transfer to work one other alternative energy.

Key words: Ecological monitoring, alternative energy, nitrogen oxide, carbon dioxide, ozone layer, "Euro-6", "Euro-7"

Introduction: Today, there is one car for every seven people in Uzbekistan will come. That is, there are more than 4 million cars on the streets of Uzbekistan is moving. because the car has advantages as well as disadvantages you can't turn a blind eye. For example, harmful smoke from cars has a negative effect on the air. In addition, car noise is a harmful sound. Today, more than 60 percent of the population of large cities in Uzbekistan suffer from the same harmful noise.

The air we breathe -each of the layers that make up the atmosphere has its own specific function. For example, the ozone layer protects all living organisms from radiation.

Ozone, formed by the presence of oxygen, nitrogen oxide and other gases under the influence of sunlight, absorbs strong ultraviolet rays and protects living organisms from its negative effects.

Exhaust gas emitted from cars is the cause of ozone depletion will be. According to experts, it is the main air pollutant in the list of anthropogenic factors, automobile transport takes the first place.

That is 40 percent of the total damage is attributable to cars moving on Earth it's right. 20 percent of the remaining damage is caused by the energy industry, 14

percent by the enterprise and production of the organization, 26 percent agricultural production, household delivered from utilities and other sectors.

The amount of pollutants released into the atmosphere	Total	Transport	Industry
2018			
By republic	2449,1	1560,3	888,7
Tashkent city	269,8	254,1	15,7
2019			
By republic	2534,6	1581,8	952,7
Tashkent city	390,5	316,0	74,5

Main part

The existing shortcomings in our republic are the fact that the produced fuels and cars do not meet the current quality level, the roads do not meet modern requirements, the lack of monitoring of air quality using automatic systems on large highways, toxicity and smoke such as the lack of thickness measuring devices attract attention.

Fuels and cars produced in our republic are not up to today's quality level. Motorways today's failure to meet modern requirements. On major highways lack of monitoring of air quality using automatic systems.

Lack of instruments for measuring toxicity and smoke thickness. According to the results of the study, the main problems in the development of electric vehicle transport are its production in a few countries of the world, the relatively high cost of the electric vehicle body, the lack of charging stations, the length of the battery charging time, and the lack of maintenance and service services.

The main pollutant substances	CO, CH, NO_x, SO₂, aldehydes, solids, etc
Steam gases throws	CO₂, CH₄

Activities conducted in the direction of atmospheric air protection

1. Updating the car fleet
2. Production of motor fuel with ecological level "Euro-6" and "Euro-7".
ensure release
3. The structure of traffic flow, the mode of traffic speed within the framework of urban development
optimization, development of the road traffic management system
4. Step-by-step transition to alternative energy types in transport
provide
5. Organization of separate lanes for passenger traffic,
with the establishment of preventive works of state environmental control of motor vehicles make it happen.

Summary

As we build a perfect lifestyle, there are huge obstacles in front of us and we need to solve problems. After all, the amount of our needs do not harm the consumption of the next generation. When to preserve nature our main goal is that each of us is environmentally safe as we want we can live in the environment. So the transport we are using prevention, neutralization and human impact of the means on the external environment. It is necessary to develop measures such as health protection.

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